

Spontaneous synchronization of oscillations between multiple cortical sites and exact fit of the wave crest with the onset of word recognition, significantly accelerate performing of a cognitive task.

Victor Vvedensky¹, Vitaly Verkhlyutov², Konstantin Gurtovoy¹.

¹ RNC Kurchatov Institute, Moscow, Russia

² Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of RAS, Moscow, Russia

VictorLvo@yandex.ru

Abstract

We measured magnetic signals of the brain during recognition of spoken words. Sometimes a subject confirms recognition very quickly ó when only just the third of the word sound was perceived. We pay special attention to these cases. Characteristic feature of these events is that during recognition process multiple cortical sites display a single oscillatory episode, specific for each location. In addition to episodes with rather irregular time course of the magnetic signal, in the comparable number of sites we see just two waves, which perfectly fit into the time window of the recognition. Moreover, the start of word perception coincides with the initial wave crest, while the crest after two waves coincides with the keystroke confirming recognition. We believe that synchronization of spontaneous oscillations with the recognition process significantly accelerates its progress.

Keywords: Word Recognition, Cortical Oscillations, Oscillatory Episodes, Magnetic Encephalography.

Introduction

In our study of spoken words perception [1] we permanently see striking random variations of the word recognition time from trial to trial. This phenomenon is common for many psychological and cognitive events [2] and is the subject of intensive research, including MEG [3, 4]. Reaction time in different experiments is unpredictable on individual trials. Spoken word recognition times for eight of our subjects are presented in Fig.1. In this plot we see considerable scatter of the duration of recognition process and individuality of each person. Recognition time variation for one subject during single experiment, about 4 minutes long, is shown in Fig.2. This plot demonstrates instability of the internal state of the subject performing cognitive task. The level of vigilance and attention fluctuate markedly, as well as the brain signals we measure.

We focused our attention on the recognition events, when subjects performed the task extraordinary quickly, in about 200 ms after word onset. This is well before the end of the word sound, which lasted 680 ms for each word. Just a couple of phonemes were perceived before the subject pressed the button, confirming recognition. There were many such events for several subjects. The points, corresponding to these events, are numerous in the lower left corner of Fig.1.

Fig.1. Word recognition times for eight subjects presented as points of different colors. Eight words were repeated 10 times each in random order. The times are shown in ascending order for each subject. Black line indicates duration of the word sound, 680 ms. Fast recognition events are concentrated in the lower left corner.

Fig.2. Variations of word recognition time for one subject (MG023) during a single experiment. These data in ordered form are presented as cyan color points in Fig.1.

Experiment

The MEG measurements were taken at the Center for Neurocognitive Research (MEG Center) of the Moscow City University of Psychology and Education using a helmet-shaped whole head 306-channel magnetometer (VectorView, Elekta Neuromag).

Sixteen volunteers took part in the study, 21 to 40 years old, 14 females, 2 males, everyone right handed. None of the participants had known neurological or psychiatric disorders or hearing deficit. All subjects signed an informed consent. The study was approved by the local ethics committee at the Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of Russian Academy of Science and was conducted following the ethical principles regarding human experimentation (Helsinki Declaration).

Before starting each experiment we determined the coordinates of anatomical reference points (left and right preauricular points and nasion) and locations of inductors, attached on the upper forehead and behind the auricles. We used the Fastrak three-dimensional digitization device (Polhemus). The signals from attached coils were used to compensate possible displacements of the subject's head in relation to the MEG sensors during measurements.

Magnetic brain responses were recorded with the sampling rate of 1000 Hz. Native hardware filters with band pass 0.1-330 Hz were used. The very low frequency (<0.5 Hz) signals and the 50-Hz power line interference and its harmonics were removed using the spatiotemporal signal separation (tSSS) method implemented in the MaxFilter program (Elekta Neuromag). The high signal-to-noise ratio provided by this measurement system made it possible to avoid narrow-band filtering and signal averaging. General data processing was done using the Brainstorm software [5].

During measurement, the subject was sitting in a magnetically shielded room. His (her) eyes were closed to avoid suppression of the alpha rhythm. The stimuli were pre-recorded words uttered by a human and delivered in earphones. The subject was instructed to recognize the heard word and to confirm recognition by a keystroke. Playback of the next word started 1 - 3 seconds after the button was pressed. In a single experiment every subject heard 80 words of the same sound duration and this measurement lasted for about 4 minutes. 8 different Russian adjectives were presented in this sequence, 10 times each in random order. Three different sets of eight adjectives close in their meaning with different word durations (680, 830, 910 ms) were presented to each subject. The choice of the particular adjectives was based on our previous experiments [6, 7], which produced highly reproducible results, provided that the group of words used in a short experiment were close in meaning. This in turn relied on the experimental findings [8], providing evidence that the semantically close words are mapped onto cortical surface in neighboring locations.

The measurement consisted of 80 alternating periods of perception of words and pauses between words. We processed signals from 204 channels, which measured gradients of the magnetic field generated by the brain. The gradient sensors are less susceptible to the distant sources and hence are more spatially selective. Each event of word recognition generated 204 different curves, which had to be compared.

Data Processing and Results

Traditional processing of brain signals, related to the external stimulus, implies signal averaging across multiple (usually about 100) trials, when the same external signal is presented. In this way experimenters try to get rid of the spontaneous (background) brain activity, which is believed to be unrelated to the processing of words. This belief is hardly well substantiated. In contrast, we try to find events in the permanently running brain signals, which are concurrent with the word recognition process. We carefully scrutinize the shape of signal curves recorded in 102 points evenly surrounding the human head. Two sensors located on a single chip measure mutually orthogonal gradients of magnetic field generated by the populations of neurons located in the region, which is called sensor's lead field and extends under the sensor from the cortical surface down to the head center. The strongest signals are produced by the neural tissue located just under the skull. Neighbor gradient sensors have somewhat overlapping lead fields, and still they reasonably well segregate contributions to the signal from different cortical areas. This comes from the specific nature of magnetic (MEG) signals, which are produced by the currents flowing parallel to the outer cortical surface. Such currents are generated by cortical polarization in brain fissures and this activity often differs considerably from the activity on the outer cortical surface, which contributes most to EEG electric potentials. In contrast to potentials, which are scalar values, the currents and gradients of magnetic field are vectors and MEG measurements, with two signals in every sensor position, provide valuable independent information. MEG increases contrast between cortical signals, since their sources may lie on different banks of a fissure or in neighboring fissures.

Being aware of these distinctive features of MEG, we analyzed each event with short recognition time individually. For this purpose, the matrix of 2 second long signal records in each of the 204 gradient channels was built for convenient visual inspection. Two columns of this matrix are shown in Fig.3. Our processing explicitly takes into account the discrete temporal structure of the encephalographic signal [9, 10]. Continuous signal can be decomposed into the sequence of segments with readily detectable sharp borders. The portion of the record between the borders can be considered as an oscillatory episode described by a number of parameters. We permanently see quick changes of the wave duration, amplitude, shape, repetition rate, as well as baseline shift or drift. Comprehensive study by Neymotin et al. [11] revealed clear evidence of oscillation events, verified by inspecting unfiltered waveforms. These events are ubiquitous in the brain.

Fig.3 shows 24 oscillatory episodes which perfectly fit into the time window of word recognition process. Episodes, which precede and follow recognition, are also indicated in different color. The signal shape in these sensors during recognition is highly peculiar, far from harmonic oscillations. On the other hand, in other 20 sensors shown in Fig.4, we see perfect fit of just two waves into the time window of interest. Moreover, the episode starts just at the crest of the wave and ends at another crest after a couple of oscillations. Fig.5 shows additional component of the word recognition process. In three sensors, the episode begins at the crest and ends at the wave trough. Usually, all tops and troughs of the waves are sharp. Oscillation events in Fig.4 and Fig.5 demonstrate presence of concurrent processes of different frequency, which coordinate instants of the wave tops and troughs. As one can see in Fig.6 all these three types of behavior are manifested in different sensors, covering considerable portion of the rear head. However sometimes, drastically different signals are recorded by two orthogonal gradient sensors located

on a single chip (65, 71, 73, 82, 92, 97 in Fig.6). This is very special case, which, probably, comes from individual layout of cortical fissures in the lead fields of the corresponding crossed sensors. Careful scrutiny of the "cortical landscape", lying under these sensors, will provide insight for description of the word recognition process. Other subjects, who from time to time recognize words very quickly, display the same set of phenomena.

Fig.3. Oscillatory episodes (24), corresponding to word recognition, highlighted in green. Episodes before and after are highlighted in grey. Left black vertical line indicates sound onset, right black line shows the instant, when the subject presses the button, confirming early completion of the task, long before the end of the word. Magenta line indicates duration of the word *pletenyj* - braided. Numbers indicate sensors where these curves were recorded. Their positions on the helmet are shown in Fig.6. Vertical plot scale is 2000 fT/cm.

Fig.4. Oscillatory episodes (20) consisting of two waves with an initial crest coinciding with the onset of the sound and an ending crest coinciding with the button press. Definitions and scales are the same as in Fig.3.

Fig.5. Three episodes, one and half waves long, where the crest coincides with word onset and wave trough with the button press. Definitions and scales are the same as in Fig.3.

Fig.6. 3D image shows positions of the magnetic sensors in the helmet over human head. Below is the top view of the helmet collapsed onto the flat surface. This makes all sensors visible in a single plot. Numbers of chips containing two orthogonal gradient sensors are indicated. The arrows show in each location the direction of cortical current generating signals, presented in Fig3, Fig.4 and Fig.5. Subject MG023.

Discussion

We see that whenever any subject hears the onset of acoustic signal, which is expected to be word, more than ten different places in the cortex abruptly change their oscillatory activity starting a new episode, which will last for some time. Later on, the oscillations switch to another episode. This happens during any word recognition, independently of the process duration. In this paper we consider only the cases, when the task is completed extremely quickly. During quick execution of the task we observe just one episode, which is concurrent with the recognition process. A number of inferences follow from this observation.

Numerous studies of signals associated with the perception of words, in particular using MEG [12], plot the time course of the process, which gradually, over several hundred milliseconds, develops from the primary sensory areas to more caudally located parts of the cortex. The basis of such a description is data obtained by averaging a large number of perception events. The averaged brain signals are very weak and they probably reflect some details of the process under study. However, our analysis of high amplitude signals in individual events gives a different picture. Just the basic topic of this article – very quick word recognition, contradicts sharply the widely accepted description of the word perception as a gradually developing process. We see that multiple cortical sites nearly immediately react at the incoming acoustic signal, when nothing indicates that this will be word and it should be recognized. This widespread reaction, most probably, occurs because the subject is pre-set in advance to solve the problem. And this happens at every trial. Primary acoustic signal is somehow broadcasted over the whole cortex and multiple scattered cortical populations of neurons become vigilant and ready to interpret the incoming signal. Since we record magnetic signals of nearly maximum possible amplitude, each activated neural population is considerably large, covering about square centimeter of cortical surface inside a cortical fissure.

In addition to the synchronized start of oscillatory episodes in 10-20 locations, the very salient feature of the whole process is simultaneous switch off of these episodes. This instant coincides with the subject's confirmation of the word recognition by a keystroke. It is tempting to conjecture that the coordinated activity of the involved set of neural populations and their unanimous vote trigger the subject's finger in the end of recognition.

The coordinated switch off of oscillatory episodes in multiple cortical sites happens when recognition terminates, independently of the process duration. The specific feature of very quick recognitions is that they run in a single oscillatory episode. In addition to episodes with quite irregular time course of the signal (Fig.3), there are those, which look like waves (Fig.4, Fig.5). It is clearly seen that the tops of the waves coincide with the sound onset. Since the word onset in our experiments was not time-locked to the running cortical oscillations, the mentioned coincidence should be considered as accidental and comparatively rare event. We really see that fast recognitions occur relatively rarely. We are forced to believe, that the exact fit of definite phase of cortical oscillations with the start of recognition process accelerates drastically the progress of cognitive process.

The topic of functional role of spontaneous oscillations in the perception process is considered in numerous studies. The general view is formulated as follows: cortical oscillations instantiate perceptual predictions by coordinating prestimulus neural activity to process the predicted

stimulus optimally [13]. Some researchers concentrate their efforts on the role of the definite phase of cortical oscillations. They see that, when a visual target presentation coincides with the trough of an alpha wave, observers are less likely to detect the target. Rapid oscillation in excitability directly influences the probability that an environmental stimulus will reach conscious awareness [14]. VanRullen et al. [15] claim that the outcome of many important brain functions depends in a periodic manner on the ongoing state of the brain, as reflected by the phase of certain pre-stimulus oscillations; and further, that it is possible to reveal this dependence using careful analysis of single-trial EEG activity. We believe that our experiments fit naturally into this mainstream of this brain research.

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